

CONCEPT OF CYBER ATTACK, LEGAL DESCRIPTION OF CRIME AND HISTORY OF DEVELOPMENT.

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Annotation

This thesis investigates the concept of cyberattacks, their legal classification as crimes, and their historical evolution. Cyber-attacks, which include a wide range of harmful acts such as hacking, phishing, and malware dissemination, pose serious hazards to individuals, businesses, and governments.

The historical progression of cyber-attacks is followed, from the beginnings of hacking to today's sophisticated and frequently state-sponsored cyber operations. This development highlights the growing complexity and significance of cyber threats, highlighting the necessity for ongoing advancements in both cybersecurity measures and legal remedies.

Keywords: Cyber-attacks, Cybercrime, Legal frameworks, Historical evolution, Digital security, Cyber law.

The technologies created by mankind are developing day by day. New technologies make human life easier and more convenient. But a second parallel process is also taking place, in addition to facilitating human life, the cases of people using it to commit crimes for their own interests are also increasing day by day. The rapid development of world digitization plays a key role in the daily increase in the number of crimes committed through computer technology, especially cyber attacks. Also, today the concept of information is seen as a real asset, thanks to which information has become one of the main objects of aggression of crimes committed by means of computer technologies.

Due to the fact that investigation and combating with cyberattacks as a crime are a difficult process, and the risk of criminals being exposed directly, as in other crimes, the number of perpetrators of this type of crime is also increasing day by day. In addition, there are also two other aspects of cyber-attack crimes: these crimes show a strong difference from other types of crimes. Firstly, these types of crimes are distinguished by the fact that they are not completely similar to the rest of the types of crimes, they are committed by means of new methods, and on the other hand, they are manifested in the fact that the crimes previously

existing in the criminal laws are committed in ways that are not available in these laws.

The dynamics and spread of the development of cyber attack crimes have made them the object of research by many criminal experts. Such crimes are studied from the point of view of criminal law, criminology, criminology, criminal procedure, victimology and many other disciplines. However, the dramatically changing nature of these types of crimes leads to significant differences in the overall definition. One of the main questions is what – cyber-attack is and how this concept relates to the terms “Cybercrime”.

“Cyberattack – is an attempt by cybercriminals to use a compromised computer system to disable computers, steal data or launch additional attacks”. Cybersecurity expert Bruce Schneier believes that cybercrime refers to criminal activity in which a computer or network is the source, target, or weapon of a crime. Cybercrime often occurs as financial gain, political purposes, or as an act of espionage.

Clifford Neumann, director of the Center for Computer Systems Security at the University of Southern California, describes computer crime as any illegal act involving a computer or network. This includes hacking, malware, denial-of-service attacks, and other forms of cybercrime. Security expert Donn Parker believes that crimes committed using computer technology: These include the use of computer technology, but are not necessarily cyber crimes or computer crimes. For example, identity theft or fraud committed using online banking services falls into this category. He also calls these crimes "computer-assisted" crimes .

Now let's look at the history of cyberattacks and crimes. For the first time, a cyber attack was used in 1966 in the US state of Minnesota to commit the crime of theft in a local bank. The following are mentioned as the most important events in the past century in computer technology crime:

- ☒ In 1973, an employee of Citybank (one of the largest and oldest banks in New York) stole two million dollars using the company's computer;
- ☒ In 1987, the first case of computer virus infection was detected in the USSR;
- ☒ the discovery of a virus that blocked 6,000 computers in the Pentagon network in 1989;
- ☒ In 1990, NASA network was sabotaged by a group of hackers for 24 hours;
- ☒ In 1995, attempt to steal \$2.8 million from Citybank using computer technology

Using cyberattack, it is possible to analyze the history of crime and determine the laws of their development. Thus, if at the beginning of the emergence of cybercrime, the main goal of the attacker was personal enrichment and the computer was used as a weapon of theft, by the 90s of the 20th century, the main goal of the person who committed the crime was "intellectual difficulty", that is, the desire to show his perfection in knowing computer systems and bypass their protection.

Nowadays, crimes of cyberattacks often become a tool of illegal political pressure. For example, in early 2009, financial institutions in India, including the State Bank, were attacked by hackers from Pakistan. In the spring of 2013, South Korea's banking system collapsed as a result of a cyber-attack. The country's authorities blamed Chinese state hackers and the special services of the DPRK.

In May 2013, US media and BBC television's internet offices were subjected to computer attacks by the Syrian Electronic Army. In addition, hackers posted information about the explosion in the White House to the press. This caused the collapse of the US stock exchanges.

As you can see, computer intervention can be used to harm the country's economic interests or security, as well as to destabilize the situation in society and even provoke unconstitutional political processes. The development of interstate integration, new means of communication, and international e-commerce has created a negative phenomenon such as criminal globalization, which among other things is manifested in high-tech fraud, intellectual piracy and money laundering.

Thus, it can be concluded that cyberattacks, along with terrorism and corruption, over time began to pose a serious threat not only to the individual or the state, but also to the entire civilization.

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